

Bolides

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***Abstract.** The composition of *Bolides* acts somewhat like a series of snapshots or a diary of my life between March 2020 and December 2021, and for me evokes geographical and temporal cues that are very specific for that particular point in time. The source material includes underwater recordings of kelp forests, captured by homemade hydrophones, the ululations of grey seal pups, and an improvised percussion performance on plate steel. The compositional methodology was guided by an aural discourse, and the structural decisions throughout the process were informed by the materials as they presented themselves, there were no abstract processes involved. Sound objects were chosen for their gestural and sonic properties, and then further processed using a mixture of real-time interaction facilitated by a Leap motion sensor and a multitouch-surface MIDI controller. Both of these devices were mapped to parameters of various DSP devices, some of which were created using Csound, some of which are native to Ableton Live 11. A series of performances were recorded using this configuration and the results of these gesturally-driven performances were further developed into the library of sound objects that make up this piece.*

1. General Information

The composition of *Bolides*¹ acts somewhat like a series of snapshots or a diary of my life between March 2020 and December 2021, and for me evokes geographical and temporal cues that are very specific for that particular point in time.

During the coronavirus lockdowns in Ireland in 2020 and 2021, the distance one could travel from their place of residence was sometimes restricted to 5km. This encouraged me to explore the town in which I had recently began renting accommodation. I had lived close to the town for most of my life but it was only during this time that I really got a chance to explore some of the lesser known (to me at least) areas in the surrounding environment. This included the wetlands on the north-east of the town, the cliffs to the south of the town and some of the secluded rocky beaches scattered along the coast. It was in these areas that much of the source material for *Bolides* was captured.

Around the time lockdown started, I had begun to swim in the sea daily, and I was regularly amazed by the clarity of the water as I swam. This was particularly true for Travelahawk, a small beach in the shadow of Wicklow's Black Castle, supposedly the first site that St. Patrick came ashore to in Ireland only to be swiftly turned away by the locals. I decided to take a GoPro into the water with me one day and I was surprised by the amount of life and colour in the kelp forests of the Wicklow coast. In addition to the sight of the sea life and surrounding kelp forest, I was immediately intrigued by the soundscape of the kelp forests. The microphone on the GoPro, whilst functional, did

¹ Link to audio: <https://bit.ly/3Rfh7gc>

not however produce clean audio recordings so, on a mission to capture clean audio recording of the kelp forests, and unbeknownst to me at the time, I began composing *Bolides*.

I initially investigated purchasing a hydrophone but my early searches resulted in finding hydrophones that I found to be a little on the expensive side, so I decided to build one myself. I began experimenting with a design I had found online in which a small electret microphone is placed within a container filled with oil. The idea is that the oil acts as an impedance transformer between the water-borne vibrations and the diaphragm of the electret microphone. I built several iterations of these hydrophones but unfortunately each one seemed to have a limited life span (the exact reasons for this are unclear to me at the time of writing this) although I did manage to capture some interesting recordings of the kelp forests as well as some lake activity and a river soundscape.

I experimented with several other designs before settling on housing a balanced phantom powered piezo inside a brass plumbing fitting and dipping the entire enclosure in PlastiDip, a liquid plastic that is used to seal and waterproof materials. Although the high frequency response of the piezo microphone was not as pronounced as the electret hydrophone, the results were still impressive for a microphone that cost well under €10 to build. I began tests with this microphone at Travelahawk beach and was pleased with the robustness of the design, so I decided to explore other parts of the vicinity such as the nearby cliff walk. The robustness of the hydrophone's design allowed me to throw it from the top of the cliffs and into the water below without issue and it was in doing this that I came across another source of sound material for this piece, grey seals.

All along the cliff walk there are several coves in which grey seals are known to reside when raising their pups between the months of August and April. As I was walking along the cliffs searching for another point at which I could drop a hydrophone, I heard some interesting ululations from what turned out to be hungry seal pups. Over the next number of weeks, I began recording these pups with the aid of a parabolic dish. The most interesting aspects of this process were discovering where exactly the pups were residing (the coves are mostly beneath the cliffs and not readily visible from land) and what times of the day they are most vocal. Needless to say, this required a lot of time spent in various scenic locations all along the Wicklow coast which was a welcome respite from the news cycle of the time.

One of the final sources of audio material in this piece came from articulations on a plate of solid steel that had originally been used as a base plate for a prop from a previous audio installation. I was moving the plate from storage when searching for materials for to build more hydrophones when I became aware of its interesting resonant properties. I set up a microphone and began improvising on the plate using my hands and with various other objects in my vicinity. When I listened back to these recordings I came across several gestures that caught my ear. It was these gestures that became the foundational sound objects around which I began to construct the entire composition.

The compositional methodology was guided by an aural discourse, and the structural decisions throughout the process were informed by the materials as they

presented themselves, there were no abstract processes involved. Sound objects were chosen for their gestural and sonic properties, and then further processed using a mixture of real-time interaction facilitated by a Leap motion sensor and a multitouch-surface MIDI controller. Both of these devices were mapped to parameters of various VSTs, some of which were created using Csound, some of which are native to Ableton Live 11. I would then record series of performances using this configuration, slowly building a new soundscape as I progressed. Finally, the results of the gesturally-driven performances of the initial sonic material were further developed into the library of sound objects that comprise this piece.

I believe in the idea that composition does not necessarily begin when material is processed, or when sound objects are arranged, or even when sources are recorded. I believe that the act of composition begins when the first steps to realising a composition are taken, in this case I think that the act of composition, or to borrow a term from Christopher Small, musicking, began when I decided to build some cheap hydrophones and explore the kelp forests of the Wicklow coast. In the 2007 documentary, *The Art of Sounds*, Pierre Henry states that “Musique Concrète is the art of decision, it’s the art of choice.” While I would not strictly define my work as Music Concrète. This sentiment rings true for my own compositional practice.

This is a stereo fixed-media piece that was intended for stereo diffusion but can be presented as a stereo file although I would like to investigate the possibility of diffusing the material in real-time using MOSCA, which allow for either ambisonic or binaural representation of the piece depending on the listener’s own setup, in conjunction with Audiomovers ListenTo or similar software.